

TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER OF REMOTELY PILOTED AIRCRAFT SYSTEMS (RPAS) FOR THE CREATIVE INDUSTRY

AIRT.EU

#AiRT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 732433.

HELPING CREATIVE INDUSTRY SMES

Although RPAS offer many creative capacities and advantages, they are not able to be used indoors. This project seeks to develop the world's first indoor RPAS specifically designed for professional use by the Creative Industries.

The main goal is to provide the Creative Industry SMEs with a tool which, by expanding the potential to use different spaces, will help them to offer new services. This in turn will increase their opportunities to grow within the European and international markets.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- Analysis of CIs needs, ethical issues and risk analysis
- Elaboration of a Green Paper for indoor use of RPAS
- Adaptation and integration of indoor positioning system
- Adaptation of RPAS
- GUI (Graphical User Interface)
- Integration and validation
- Demonstration

POTENTIAL USES

Aerial photography and filming:

- TV
- Events
- Short films
- Publicity
- Heritage

Motion Capture:

- Video games
- Cinema

AiRT consortium brings together a group of four partners from three European countries with a complementary and outstanding range of experiences, skills, competences and resources essential to achieve the innovation objectives: the world's first indoor RPAS designed for professional use by CIs.

Universitat Politècnica de València
Creative Industries + ICT

Pozyx
Indoor positioning system ICT-SME

Aerotools
RPAS manufacturing ICT-SME

Clearhead
Creative agency